

INFLUENCE OF NATURAL-CLIMATE FACTORS ON ROAD AND VEHICLE CONDITIONS

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Abstract. The article is devoted to the problem of the influence of natural and climatic factors on roads. Influence of natural and climatic factors on road construction, regularities of the moisture-thermal regime of the road base. The rise of the road surface from the ice on the roads (deep). The influence of natural and climatic factors on the surface of the road surface and the conditions for the movement of cars is presented.

Key words: natural and climatic factors, road surface, highways, soil properties.

ВЛИЯНИЕ ПРИРОДНО-КЛИМАТИЧЕСКИХ ФАКТОРОВ НА ДОРОЖНО-АВТОМОБИЛЬНЫЕ УСЛОВИЯ

Аннотация. Статья посвящена проблеме влияния природно-климатических факторов на автомобильные дороги. Влияние природно-климатических факторов на дорожное строительство, закономерности влаготеплового режима дорожного основания. Подъем дорожного покрытия ото льда на дорогах (глубокий). Представлено влияние природно-климатических факторов на поверхность дорожного покрытия и условия движения автомобилей.

Ключевые слова: природно-климатические факторы, дорожное покрытие, автомобильные дороги, свойства грунта.

Climate and weather are components of natural factors that significantly affect the transport and operational characteristics of roads, the mode and safety of traffic, that is, the driving conditions on the road and the mode of its operation. Roads are subject to constant and varied impacts of natural factors. These effects can be divided into two types:

- *impact on the condition of the floor and pavement as a supporting structure, resulting in changes in its strength, durability and performance characteristics;*
- *affects the state of the road surface as if it were a slippery surface, as a result of which the state of this surface changes, rolling resistance, road grip and, as a result, the interaction of the car with the road worsen.*

In addition, the condition of the car and the driver is influenced by natural and climatic factors, as well as the entire environment, that is, all driving conditions.

Weather, weather conditions, weather conditions and meteorological conditions are used as synonyms and mean the state of the atmosphere, characterized by a set of values of meteorological phenomena, factors or elements at a certain time in a certain place Climate or meteorological phenomena, elements (factors) - individual characteristics of atmospheric conditions observed on weather stations (atmospheric pressure, temperature, air humidity, wind, precipitation, fog, blizzard, etc., as well as their combination). Each meteorological factor is characterized by the probability of occurrence (recurrence), duration of impact and subsequent impact, intensity. Information on the duration and intensity of exposure can be found in climate guides or obtained from the nearest weather station on the road.

Climate (climatic conditions) is a statistical regime of weather conditions over a long period of time (from a year to several decades), that is, it is a natural sequence of atmospheric processes in a certain area, the weather characteristic of this area sets the weather regime. The **microclimate** is the climate of a small area, due to differences in topography, vegetation, soil conditions, water bodies, buildings, etc. The influence of metrological factors on conditions is transmitted through the state of the road surface, the interaction of the car with the road and the driver's perception of traffic conditions, this means regular seasonal changes in the sublayer and overlying layers. humidity and temperature.

Complex processes take place in the road structure (covering + subgrade): heating, cooling, freezing, melting, evaporation, condensation, sublimation (a substance passes through a liquid and immediately passes from a solid state to a gaseous state). As a result, processes of heat and mass transfer or heat and moisture diffusion (HWM) regularly occur in the road structure, causing changes in humidity and temperature.

In spring, the ground first melts under the road surface. At this time, the ice migrates from top to bottom under the action of the liquid potential and its own mass and turns into a liquid phase, which remains in the frozen, practically impermeable ground. A few days later, a water-saturated state appears on the surface of the frozen soil - the upper part of the road surface under the subgrade (Pic.5). The road surface loses strength, is destroyed by traffic, its material is mixed with liquefied soil.

The impact of environmental factors on the road causes heat and moisture exchange in the layers of the pavement and the road. This is a complex and interrelated process. Changes in temperature cause migration (slow movement) of moisture. The accumulation of moisture and the transition of moisture into another form contribute to the transfer of heat. Therefore, the processes of heat and moisture exchange should be considered jointly. It has been established that the soil and layers of coatings are breathable, and the holes in them communicate with each other. Consequently, in the soil and floor layers there are conditions for mass transfer: air exchange and vapor exchange. If soil moisture is less than its total moisture capacity, exchange is possible, i.e. $W_1 > W_2$. At full moisture capacity, all the pores of the soil are filled with a liquid phase and air and vapor exchange stops.

In water-unsaturated soils, moisture is in a two-phase state: W_p - water vapor is always in a saturated state (relative humidity of air vapor $d \approx 100\%$) and W_l - liquid phase. The phase ratio is constantly changing and depends on the total soil moisture. In frozen soils, an additional solid phase appears - ice, the amount of which is proportional to the value of t_b . At soil temperatures t_T below 0°C , not all liquid phases turn into ice, partly due to salinity and molecular forces arising from soil particles. The temperature of ice formation, depending on the mineralogical composition of the soil, ranges from -0.5°C to -2.5°C for sands. Even at very low soil temperatures at $t_g = -20...-50^\circ\text{C}$, part of the liquid phase does not freeze. Therefore, the diffusion of water vapor, the migration of the liquid phase and the formation of ice occur throughout the winter period. The liquid phase evaporates and freezes, and the water vapor condenses into a liquid or solid phase. Heat transfer in road structures occurs due to three components. The main part of the heat is transferred from particle to particle due to thermal conduction (conduction). The second component of heat transfer is the heat of phase transitions

during freezing - melting, condensation - evaporation, oblimentation - sublimation. The third, convective, component of heat transfer is insignificant (2...3%) and can be neglected.

The liquid phase moves due to the presence of two potentials - concentration and temperature. Due to the first potential, the liquid phase moves from areas of high humidity to areas of low humidity (concentration migration). This potential prevails when the liquid phase is displaced (95...98%). Due to the second potential, thermal migration of the liquid phase occurs in the amount of 2...5%. Thus, if two soil zones with the same temperature but different humidity ($W_1 > W_2$) come into contact, there will be migration from areas with higher humidity (W_1) to areas with lower humidity (W_2). This can be explained as follows. With an increase in humidity W_1 , the thickness of the water film increases, r decreases, r increases, and the vapor pressure p_n compressible by the water film increases. In this case, p_1 increases. Since $p_1 > p_2$, moisture moves from zone W_1 to zone W_2 .

Road surface during soil thawing:

1 - liquefied soil; 2 - water units; 3 - line of soil freezing; GWL - groundwater level

When the wheels of the car hit the bottom, water accumulates on the surface of the road through the cracks. As the soil thaws, moisture moves to the lower layers of the soil. Humidity begins to decrease, soil strength increases, and subsidence stabilizes.

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